

DELAMINATION CHARACTERISTICS OF A LAMINATED PLATE SUBJECTED TO A DEEPENING EXTERNAL PART-THROUGH HOLE

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ABSTRACT

A finite element procedure using stacked plate elements to model composite laminates behavior has been used to investigate the delamination characteristics of a plate subjected to a deepening part-through hole. The flat plate model represents an idealization of a composite pressure vessel. Bi-axial tensile loads were applied to simulate the loads due to internal pressure. A virtual crack closure technique was used to determine strain energy release rate distributions along the delamination front for various part-through hole depths and crack lengths and locations. For a 1 cm diameter part-through hole, the energy for growing delaminations is generally non-uniform as a function of angular position, especially for those located at an interface between 0° and 77° plies. Delamination growth is expected to be more favorable in the hoop direction and is quite stable under most conditions.

Keywords: delamination, composite laminates, layered finite elements, strain energy release rates, part-through hole

1. INTRODUCTION

When a composite pressure vessel is subjected to a concentrated laser ablation process, three outcomes may occur: (1) burst resulting in a complete loss of structural integrity, (2) vent or depressurization with no large-scale loss of structural integrity, or (3) a combination of both which results in limited loss of structural integrity. The progressively deepening part-through hole creates a very complicated stress state in the region of the part-through hole due to the stress concentration and interlaminar stresses at the "newly" created free edges. The failure resulting from these stresses generally consists of two primary modes: in-plane failure within the plies (matrix cracking and fiber breakage), and out-of-plane failure between the plies (delamination). The ultimate failure will consist of some combination and interaction of the failure modes. The overall goal of this research is to provide a more in-depth understanding of the failure process by developing modeling procedures that include both failure modes explicitly. The focus of this paper, however, is on modeling delaminations and investigating their characteristics. The capability to explicitly model delamination at any ply interface is achieved by discretizing each

ply of the composite laminate with a layer of plate finite elements at the neutral surface. Similar approaches have been taken by Wilt et al. [1], who used layered finite elements to model sublaminates, and Fuehne [2], who used a penalty method to constrain layers of elements.

2. METHODOLOGY

Laminate behavior is enforced by tying elements in adjacent layers together through a series of kinematic constraints. The kinematic constraints relating displacements and rotations at corresponding nodes in adjacent plies (denoted A and B) are given by

$$u_A - u_B - (X_A - X_B) \left[\frac{\cos \phi_y^A + \cos \phi_y^B}{2} - 1 \right] - (Z_A - Z_B) \left[\frac{\sin \phi_y^A + \sin \phi_y^B}{2} \right] = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$v_A - v_B - (Y_A - Y_B) \left[\frac{\cos \phi_x^A + \cos \phi_x^B}{2} - 1 \right] - (Z_A - Z_B) \left[\frac{\sin \phi_x^A + \sin \phi_x^B}{2} \right] = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$w_A - w_B - (Z_A - Z_B) \left[\frac{\cos \phi_y^A + \cos \phi_y^B}{2} - 1 \right] + (X_A - X_B) \left[\frac{\sin \phi_y^A + \sin \phi_y^B}{2} \right] - (Z_A - Z_B) \left[\frac{\cos \phi_x^A + \cos \phi_x^B}{2} - 1 \right] - (Y_A - Y_B) \left[\frac{\sin \phi_x^A + \sin \phi_x^B}{2} \right] = 0 \quad (3)$$

where u_A , v_A and w_A are the displacements of a node on the neutral surface of ply A (i.e. individual plate elements) in the global X , Y and Z directions, respectively, and ϕ_x^A , ϕ_y^A and ϕ_z^A are the rotations about each axis. Also, X_A , Y_A , and Z_A are the undeformed coordinates of the node in ply A . Similar definitions apply for the corresponding node on adjacent ply B . Using this process, each node in ply A is constrained to the corresponding node in ply B , and this process is repeated for each layer. Applying this constraint enforces continuity of displacements at ply interfaces while retaining independence of rotations within each ply. The kinematic constraint was entered through a user written subroutine in the commercial finite element code ABAQUS [3]. With laminate behavior thus enforced, delaminations can be modeled quite readily by simply relaxing the kinematic constraint at the appropriate ply interface.

In order to characterize the propensity of delamination cracks to grow, strain energy release rates are calculated along the delamination front. A method was developed to determine the total strain energy release rate, as well as the individual components, by adapting the virtual crack closure technique [4,5] for the layered plate element configuration. These equations are

$$G_I = \frac{F_n u_n}{2 \Delta W}, \quad G_{II} = \frac{F_t u_t}{2 \Delta W}, \quad G_{III} = \frac{F_s u_s}{2 \Delta W} \quad (4)$$

and

$$G_{TOT} = G_I + G_{II} + G_{III} \quad (5)$$

where Δ and W are the delamination element tip length and width, respectively. Also, the quantities F_n , F_t , F_s and u_n , u_t , u_s are transformed global forces and relative crack opening displacements behind the crack tip, respectively. These quantities are transformed from the global coordinate system (X, Y, Z) to a local crack tip coordinate system (t, s, n) where the tangential axis t bisects the local delamination opening, s is tangent to the delamination front, and n is normal to the plane bisecting the delamination surfaces (parallel to $s \times t$). This transformation is necessary since the delamination tip may undergo large rotations. Under the transformation, the strain energy release rate components G_I , G_{II} , and G_{III} are interpreted as the local mode I, mode II, and mode III components, respectively.

Since the delamination tip is not represented explicitly by the finite element model, but rather implicitly modeled by the constraint, nodal forces and displacements at the delamination tip are not directly determined as part of the finite element solution. Crack tip closure forces are essentially the forces of the constraint between the two plies immediately above and below the delamination crack. These forces can be derived from the resultants of the non-zero nodal forces in all the elements above or below the delamination. Crack opening displacement components are determined by first calculating the coordinates of the points on each surface of the delamination. The coordinates of each point are extrapolated from the displacements and rotations of the neutral surface of the plies bounding the delamination as given by

$$x^* = X + u \pm \frac{t}{2} \sin \phi_x \quad (6)$$

$$y^* = Y + v \pm \frac{t}{2} \sin \phi_y \quad (7)$$

$$z^* = Z + w \pm \frac{t}{2} \cos \phi_x \cos \phi_y \quad (8)$$

where the superscript asterisk (*) denotes a point on the delamination surface and t is the ply thickness. The sign for the \pm term depends on whether the delamination surface requires extrapolation above or below the neutral surface of the ply. The relative crack opening displacements behind the delamination tip are then determined according to

$$u^* = x_I^* - x_J^* \quad , \quad v^* = y_I^* - y_J^* \quad , \quad w^* = z_I^* - z_J^* \quad (9)$$

where I and J are points that were originally coincident at the ply interface before delamination. The crack tip forces and displacements are then transformed to the local crack tip coordinate system and substituted into Equations 4-5 to determine strain energy release rates.

3. PLATE MODEL

Curvature has been neglected initially and a flat laminated plate used to model the pressure vessel. A square plate with a part-through hole and unequal bi-axial tension (to simulate pressure vessel loading) is shown in Figure 1. The plate is 10 cm square and has a total thickness of 0.22352 cm, which is composed of eight plies of 0.02794 cm each. The layup is $[0^\circ/0^\circ/\pm 77^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/\pm 77^\circ]$, which corresponds to an actual hoop/helix layup in a pressure vessel test specimen. The material system is an S-glass/epoxy with the following elastic constants:

$$\begin{array}{lll}
E_{11} = 53.7 \text{ GPa}, & \nu_{12} = 0.272, & G_{12} = 4.59 \text{ GPa} \\
E_{22} = 15.3 \text{ GPa}, & \nu_{23} = 0.535, & G_{23} = 3.23 \text{ GPa} \\
E_{33} = 15.3 \text{ GPa}, & \nu_{31} = 0.078, & G_{31} = 4.59 \text{ GPa}.
\end{array}$$

The laser ablation process was modeled as a part-through hole with a diameter of 1.0 cm and a variable depth. The depth depended on the number of plies removed. The delamination process was modeled by introducing delaminations of uniform radial lengths from the center of the plate. Delaminations were located at ply interfaces along the free surface of the inside of the hole. Since the hoop/helix layup does not strictly permit material planes of symmetry, whole plate, half plate, and quarter plate models have been investigated in previous work. The results suggest that quarter plate symmetry about the XZ and YZ planes is possible with some marginal error near the X and Y axes. Therefore, quarter symmetry was assumed for the current study, as indicated by the sample finite element mesh in Figure 3. Note that this mesh is repeated for each ply in a laminated composite model. Symmetry boundary conditions were applied to nodes along X and Y axes, and a grip condition was simulated along the exterior edges of the plate. Finally, unequal bi-axial tensile loads were also applied along these axes: 67,294 N in the hoop direction (X -direction) and 33,646 N in the longitudinal direction (Y -direction). These loads create the same stresses as for a 25.4 cm diameter pressure vessel with an internal pressure of 10.6 MPa.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Several situations were modeled in order to investigate delamination characteristics as measured by strain energy release rate distributions. These distributions represent the energy supplied to the delamination for growth at discrete points along the delamination front, using θ as the tangential coordinate or angular position along the crack front. Note from Figure 2 that $\theta=0^\circ$ corresponds to the X -axis and $\theta=90^\circ$ corresponds to the Y -axis.

Total strain energy release rate (G_T) distributions for a single delamination of 0.25 cm in radial length located at the bottom of the part-through hole are shown in Figure 3 for part-through hole depths (s) of 2, 3, and 4 plies. The delamination depths (c) are the same as the hole depths for all three cases (i.e. $s=c$), but the layups of the plies bounding the delaminations are different. The delamination located 2 plies deep is at the $0^\circ/+77^\circ$ interface, the delamination 3 plies deep is at the $\pm 77^\circ$ interface, and the delamination 4 plies deep is at the $-77^\circ/0^\circ$ interface. A general feature of all three curves is that the energy supplied to the delamination front is quite non-uniform, with the largest amount of energy being supplied to the region of the delamination near the X -axis ($\theta < 45^\circ$). This non-uniformity suggests that a delamination will likely extend in an uneven, or non-uniform, manner. Specifically, delaminations are more likely to grow in the hoop direction than the longitudinal direction. This is particularly true for the $0^\circ/+77^\circ$ interface because the variation is most extreme for this case. The energy supplied to the delamination is generally more uniform for the other two cases, with the delamination energy being suppressed for $\theta < 45^\circ$ and enhanced for $\theta > 45^\circ$, relative to the 2 ply case. This behavior is attributed more to the effects of unequal bi-axial loading and the fiber orientation of the plies bounding the delamination, rather than to the effects of increasing the depth of the part-through hole and the delamination. The 3 and 4 ply deep delaminations both have a helix layer directly above the delamination, mitigates the variation in strain energy release rate somewhat. Since the helix layers have fibers that are oriented at $\pm 77^\circ$ with the X -axis, they behave essentially as fibers with a 90° orientation, i.e. they have much higher stiffness in the longitudinal direction than do 0° fibers. As a result, when helix layers are above the delamination a greater proportion of the longitudinal load is carried by these plies. Near the X -axis ($\theta < 45^\circ$) the hoop stresses generally tend to peel away the plies above the delamination and the longitudinal load in these plies reduces or suppresses this tendency. Near

the Y -axis ($\theta > 45^\circ$) the opposite occurs: the energy for delamination is enhanced because the helix layers carry more longitudinal load causing more peeling away. Comparing the 3 and 4 ply cases, the delamination energy is lower for the 4 ply model because the crack is located between the $\pm 77^\circ$ layers and this minimizes the material mismatch between the plies bounding the delamination.

The strain energy release rate distributions in Figure 4 simulate delamination growth in a radially uniform manner. Delamination lengths of 0.25 cm, 0.50 cm, and 0.75 cm have been investigated. The delamination is located at the bottom of the part-through hole at the $0^\circ/+77^\circ$ interface ($s=c=2$ plies). Increasing the radial length of the delamination results in a consistent decrease in the strain energy release rate distributions, indicating that delamination growth is a stable process. Also, these distributions suggest that as a delamination extends, the energy supplied for delamination becomes even more concentrated in the hoop direction, i.e. near the X -axis ($\theta < 45^\circ$). The effect of increasing the part-through hole depth while keeping the delamination at a fixed depth of 2 plies ($0^\circ/+77^\circ$ interface) and a radial length of 0.25 cm is illustrated in Figure 5. Increasing the part-through hole depth decreases the energy supplied to the delamination for growth, indicating that delamination growth stabilizes with further material removal beyond the ply interface where the delamination is located. Note as well that the non-uniform shape of the strain energy release rate distributions generally remains the same.

The versatility of the procedures developed permits simultaneous modeling of multiple delaminations located at different ply interfaces and having different lengths. A specific case is presented in Figure 6 for three delaminations with different locations and lengths. The inset in the figure shows the delamination locations and lengths. The part-through hole depth has been held constant at 4 plies deep. The strain energy release rate distributions indicate that the delamination located at the $0^\circ/+77^\circ$ interface is most likely to grow in the hoop direction (along the X -axis), whereas the other two delaminations would be expected to grow more uniformly as indicated by their fairly uniform distributions. Another noteworthy aspect of these results is the relative effect that multiple delaminations have upon continued delamination growth. Comparing the results for the 0.25 cm delamination at the $-77^\circ/0^\circ$ interface in Figure 6 with results for the corresponding delamination length and location in Figure 4 shows that the energy release rate distribution has been significantly reduced by the presence of the other two cracks. Similar comparisons may be made with other corresponding situations. The implication of this result is again that delamination growth is a stable process since the presence of previously created delaminations tends to reduce the energy supplied to subsequent delaminations.

The results presented herein highlight several trends for the configuration studied. Strain energy release rates at the crack front are generally non-uniform suggesting that delaminations will likely grow preferentially in the hoop direction for most conditions. Increasing the part-through hole depth and delamination length tend to decrease the strain energy release rates. Multiple delaminations also reduce the strain energy release rates. Finally, the results indicate that delamination growth is expected to be a stable process under most conditions for the cases studied.

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Figure 1. Composite plate with a part-through hole.

Figure 2. Sample finite element mesh for quarter symmetry plate model.

Figure 3. Total strain energy release rates for single 0.25 cm delaminations.

Figure 4. Strain energy release rates for three delamination lengths.

Figure 5. Strain energy release rates for three part-through hole depths.

Figure 6. Strain energy release rates for three multiple delaminations.